

1 Article

2 Past, present and future monitoring at the Vallcebre 3 landslide (Eastern Pyrenees, Spain)

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10 **Featured Application: Monitoring of very slow landslides with Classical and Novel Techniques.**

11 **Abstract:** The works carried out for monitoring the displacements of Vallcebre landslide (Pyrenees
12 range, NE of Spain) since 1987 are presented. The landslide, which extends over an area of about 0.8
13 km² and affects more than 20 *10⁶ m³, has experienced displacements up to one meter per year in
14 some points and periods. It has been periodically monitored since 1987, using a wide range of
15 surface and in-hole techniques: triangulation with theodolite, Terrestrial Photogrammetry,
16 Electronic Distance Measurement, GNSS-GPS, inclinometers, wire extensometers, piezometers,
17 DInSAR (satellite) and GBSAR (terrestrial). The results using the new techniques have been
18 compared with those obtained with the GNSS-GPS and the wire extensometer, and checked against
19 fixed stable points. From this comparison, we conclude that even though wire extensometers and
20 inclinometers may have the highest precision, in practice all the systems have their own role in
21 providing meaningful data for the monitoring at different study stages. In the near future, we
22 envisage the installation of a Distributed Fiber Optic array to monitor the risk with a certain space
23 and time continuity. After the evaluation of the precision and advantages of the different methods,
24 the complementary use of some of them is strongly recommended.

25 **Keywords:** Monitoring, Landslides, Photogrammetry, Global Positioning System, in-hole wire
26 extensometer, DInSAR, GBSAR

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28 1. Introduction and site description

29 The Vallcebre landslide is located in the Eastern Pyrenees, approximately 125 km north of
30 Barcelona, Spain (Fig. 1). Its situation, geological context and complete geomorphological description
31 can be found in [1, 2]. The present paper is an expanded and updated version of a previous work [3]
32 where we described the landslide as a translational slide with a stair-shape profile. As in most
33 landslides, its structure and behaviour are not simple. The landslide is 1200 m long and 600 m wide,
34 involving an area of 0.8 km², which shows superficial cracking and distinct ground displacements
35 (Fig. 2). The mobilised material consists of a set of shale, gypsum and claystone layers gliding over a
36 thick limestone bed. A geological cross-section is presented later in section 2.4 (Fig. 10). The average
37 slope of both the topography and the basal shear surface in the middle and lower unit are gentle, in
38 the range between 6 and 10°. The basal shear surface depth is 42m in the middle unit and 15m in the
39 lower one, being quite planar for the most part of the sliding surface.

40 Figure 3 shows a geomorphological sketch of the landslide and the location of the monitored
41 points and boreholes. The most active area is the lower unit, whose toe is being eroded continuously
42 by the Vallcebre torrent. Consequently, most of the monitored points were located there.

57 **Figure 1.** Location of Vallcebre valley (red arrow) within the Pyrenees range, NE of Spain.

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75 **Figure 2.** General view of the Vallcebre landslide from W. The unstable area (yellow contour) is about
76 0.8 km², has an average slope of only 17° (green line), and is sliding as a translational slide. The white
77 arrows are the average slide directions of the upper, middle and lower units, which are separated by
78 scarp zones (dashed yellow lines).

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103 **Figure 3.** Geomorphological scheme of the Vallcebre landslide superimposed over a vertical aerial
104 image. Several GPS benchmarks, corner reflectors and borehole extensometers have been highlighted
105 with symbols.

106 The measurement of displacements is very often the simplest way to observe the evolution of a
107 landslide and to analyse either the kinematics of the movement, the response to the triggering
108 conditions (e.g. rainfall) or the efficiency of corrective measures.

109 A variety of measuring techniques have been developed to track the movements of unstable
110 areas (see i.e. [4, 5]). This second work, also known as the ‘Red Book’ of Geotechnical Instrumentation
111 and Monitoring, is due to John Dunnycliff, who has recently passed away.

112 Several of these methods have been used in Vallcebre since 1987, beginning with “classical”
113 surveying and photogrammetry, and using GPS from 1995. In 1996, this site was included in the
114 frame of the NEWTECH Project funded by the European Commission. Between July 1996 and March
115 1997, 14 boreholes were drilled in the slope and equipped with inclinometers, wire extensometers
116 and open standpipe piezometers (Fig. 3).

117 In 2004-2005 multipoint piezometers were installed in three additional boreholes. Later, the
118 Vallcebre landslide was included in a EU-FP7-funded research project known as SAFELAND. In 2007
119 seven artificial radar corner reflectors (CR) were installed to test the DInSAR monitoring capabilities.
120 In 2010-2011, still within the SAFELAND project, the lower part of the landslide was monitored using
121 a Ground-Based SAR (GBSAR). In this sense, the Vallcebre landslide can be considered to be a real-
122 scale laboratory where the performance of different monitoring techniques can be assessed and
123 compared. For instance, Laser Scanning (both Terrestrial or Aerial) have been disregarded because
124 the ground displacements, mainly parallel to the topography, would be difficult to detect; also the
125 vegetation would mask the results

126 In the paper, section 2 describes the measuring systems. In section 3, some results are presented
127 and compared in terms of precision and repeatability. Finally, some conclusions are outlined

128 regarding the advantages and drawbacks of the systems tested in Vallcebre. This comparison has
129 been done in terms of cost, ease of use, precision and continuity of the results.
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131 2. Monitoring methods used in Vallcebre and sample results

132 A summary of the monitoring systems used consecutively from 1987 to the present in Vallcebre
133 is given here. More details can be found in [1, 6, 7, 8, 9].
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135 2.1. Terrestrial photogrammetry

136 The first monitoring network established on the landslide was based on terrestrial (or “close-
137 range”) photogrammetry. A total of seven campaigns were performed at the landslide foot between
138 1987 and 1992, covering only a small area of about 100 x 50 m (Fig. 4). Stereopairs were taken with a
139 Wild P32 metric camera (Fig. 4). Each campaign included three photograms that produced two
140 photogrammetric models.

141 The results of each survey were the change in the coordinates of the main points (displacements).
142 The precision ranges between 1 cm in well-defined points (pointing targets for instance) and 10 cm
143 (rock blocks, trees and so on). Maps with contour lines were also produced (Fig. 5). The interpretation
144 of this kind of maps is not simple: the variations of the terrain surface are caused by the landslide
145 movement, but also by the soil erosion during rainfalls and the eroding effect of the Vallcebre Torrent
146 at the base of the toe. Although several blocks exhibit displacement of up to 8 m, the variation of the
147 contour lines is very moderate as a whole (Fig. 5).

148 At that time, the use of terrestrial photogrammetry in landslides was not straightforward,
149 because of the difficulty of creating a proper set-up with an adequate view over the hill slope.
150 Moreover, specialized and costly equipment had to be available for a precise stereocompilation.
151 Although out of the scope of this paper, it is worth to say that the photogrammetry processing has
152 evolved in the last decade towards automation, ease of use and low cost, thanks to the so-called
153 Structure from Motion (SfM) concept (10, 11, 12). In parallel, the use of drones (or UAS) as aerial
154 photogrammetry platforms permits to overcome the point-of-view issues during acquisition (11, 12,
155 13, 14, 15, 16). In this way, photogrammetry is once again a powerful landslide monitoring technique,
156 providing information that is almost continuous in space, but discontinuous in time.

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172 **Figure 4.** Left: example of a 6 x 8 cm glass plate photograph of landslide toe taken from the Vallcebre
173 Torrent. Right: Wild P32 camera for terrestrial photogrammetry over a theodolite, which was used
174 for the landslide toe monitoring between 1987 and 1992.

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Figure 5. Terrestrial photogrammetry sample result: Map of differences between two campaigns (one meter contour-line interval) at the landslide toe (Fig. 4).

2.2. Triangulation and Electronic Distance Measurement

From 1987 to 1995, geodetic measurements with theodolite and EDM (Electronic Distance Measurement) were carried out. Between 1987 and 1992, up to 17 points were triangulated in the toe of the lower unit, mainly for orientation of the photogrammetric models (Fig. 6a). In the period 1988-1994, three additional points in the middle unit were monitored with single distance variation measurements (Fig. 6b). During 1994 and 1995, a "triangulation" from new base benchmarks E1 and E2 (Fig. 6c) was extended to 16 points spread out through the whole landslide. The angle measurements were carried out with a Wild T2 theodolite, and the EDM with a Wild DIOR 3002S.

The rate of movement measured during the period 1987-1995 was strongly dependent on the rainfall and the target position within the landslide. Rates up to 4 m per year were observed at certain points near the toe in the rainy years, while almost no displacement occurred during periods of drought (Fig. 7). In the middle landslide unit (Fig. 3), the rate of displacement was significantly smaller, in the range of 1 to 30 cm/year.

In terms of the precision of the observations, the EDM measurements proved to be more reliable (typically 1cm) than angle measurements with theodolites (around 4 cm at typical distances), at least with the set-up, equipment and sighting distances in use in Vallcebre. This is due to the fact that the precise determination of angles needed greater experience and better environmental conditions (no mist or smog in the line of sight, proper target illumination, lack of air vibration due to strong insolation and so on), often not completely available in mountain areas at the time when the measurements have to be taken.

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229 **Figure 6.** Schemes for the triangulation (a), single distance variation (b) and triangulation (c)
230 methods as used in the Vallcebre landslide from 1987 to 1995.

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242 **Figure 7.** First tentative correlation between the displacement of a point in the lower unit (mm, black
243 line) and the cumulative rainfall (mm, blue line), during 1994-1995.

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245 2.3. The GPS-GNSS surveys

246 Following the discussion on the precision of the observations, the expected errors for the Global
 247 Positioning System (1 to 2 cm, depending on the method in use [7]) are lower when compared to
 248 theodolite and EDM errors. Additionally, the GPS precision is more balanced in the three axes (see
 249 Fig. 21). These facts led us to apply GPS techniques to perform systematic monitoring of the Vallcebre
 250 landslide. In December 1995, a complete double survey (EDM and GPS) was carried out in order to
 251 link the measurements taken with classical methods with the first GPS campaign. The equipment
 252 used then was a Trimble 4000 SSi model with two dual frequency receivers (Fig. 8). Currently, we are
 253 using two Topcon HiperPro dual constellation receivers (Fig. 23).

254 Most of the old targets were recovered with minor modifications. As new points have been
 255 added since 1996, the monitoring network has now around 50 points (Fig. 3), consisting on
 256 engravings in rock blocks outcropping in the hillside, steel rods, stakes, and the top of the casing of
 257 the inclinometric boreholes (Fig. 8); the radar Corner Reflectors vertexes have been used as well (Fig.
 258 23). There are seven additional points on the limestone around the sliding zone. These were the fixed
 259 points used to check the GPS accuracy. This network allowed both the measurement of displacements
 260 and the comparison with movements obtained with the borehole equipment (inclinometers and wire
 261 extensometers) and the Radar measurements.

262 Although the Fast-Static GPS method (more precise and robust) was partly applied in the first
 263 years, the RTK (Real Time Kinematic) is currently in use for productivity reasons [7]. Currently, we
 264 can measure the entire network within a single day, travelling across the slope by car and on foot.
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267 **Figure 8.** Examples of Vallcebre monitoring points with different antenna set-up: telescopic pole (a);
 268 pole with mini-tripod (b); ground-plane antenna over a tripod, centered with an optical plummet over
 269 an inclinometer borehole (c)

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271 **Figure 9.** Examples of results of the GPS monitoring a) planimetric displacements from the initial
 272 position in the period 1995-1998 b) planimetric movement of one point during the yearly campaigns.

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 274 Fourteen GPS campaigns were out from carried December 1995 to February 1998, one survey
 275 every 2 months approximately (Fig. 9a). Later on, the campaigns were continued on a yearly basis
 276 (Fig. 9b), 36 GPS surveys until now. More details about the GPS and special considerations for its
 277 application to landslide monitoring can be found in [7, 17, 18].
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279 *2.4. In-hole (or geotechnical) instrumentation*

280 Between July 1996 and March 1997, 14 boreholes were drilled in the slope for reconnaissance; 3
 281 more were drilled in 2005 (Fig. 10). Some of them were equipped with inclinometers, wire
 282 extensometers and open standpipe piezometers. Inclinometers and piezometers were standard
 283 devices. As an example, Fig. 11 shows one inclinometer head and its typical record, where the slip
 284 surface is clearly marked. Measurements were made every 2-3 weeks until the casing deformation
 285 prevented the safe and proper sliding of the probe.
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292 **Figure 10.** NE-SW geological cross-section of the Vallcebre landslide according to [2]. Some of the 17
 293 boreholes drilled are shown, which were equipped with inclinometers, wire extensometers (for shear
 294 displacement) and vibrating wire piezometers.

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307 **Figure 11.** Left: view of the head of a borehole during the measurement with the inclinometer. Right:
 308 graph with the successive displacement profiles from August 1996 to December 1997. The main slip
 309 surface appeared to be 34 m deep.

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On the other hand, the extensometers were wire-type, specially built following a previous design of [19]. They consist of a protected steel wire anchored to the bedrock, below the slip surface, inside a piezometric pipe (Fig. 12). After some computation, the wire displacement at the pulley can be related with the horizontal displacement of the landslide (Fig. 13). We can quote two major advantages of this device. Firstly, with a potentiometer, it allows the continuous recording of the displacement, particularly necessary to collect information during the concentrated rainfall periods, characteristic of the Mediterranean climates (Fig. 14). Secondly, the wire extensometer works properly with big landslide displacements, much larger than the 20-30 cm that would typically break the inclinometric pipe; in fact, in 2012, 16 years after their installation, 3 wire extensometers were still working, with a cumulated total wire displacement of up to 6 meters. Full details of the wire extensometer can be found in [6].

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Figure 12. Head of one of the borehole wire extensometers installed at Vallcebre. The cable for the piezometer (black) can also be appreciated.

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Figure 13. Sketch of the borehole wire extensometer. Left: just after installation. Right: after some shear displacement of the landslide (idealized). The relationship between the wire displacement at the pulley and the horizontal displacement of the landslide depends on the width of the shear zone and the borehole diameter [6]. The smaller the borehole diameter, the faster the wire response.

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331 **Figure 14.** Measurements at borehole S2. Above: rate of displacement derived from the wire
 332 extensometer. Below: groundwater table fluctuation measured by the piezometer. A perfect
 333 synchronism between rate and water level can be appreciated.
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335 2.5. DInSAR monitoring using corner reflectors

336 The Space Borne SAR monitoring of landslides has been reported in [20, 21, 22] among others.
 337 When applying DInSAR to landslide monitoring in forested areas, a condition that is difficult to fulfil
 338 is that a sufficient number of targets within the area of interest remain coherent during the
 339 observation period. One way to overcome this limitation is the deployment of artificial corner
 340 reflectors (CRs) that ensure coherent, high-quality DInSAR estimates. Using CRs, however, demands
 341 additional resources; it also prevents historical deformation studies based on archive SAR imagery.

342 After a detailed discussion of the Vallcebre site suitability for DInSAR with CRs, [8] describe the
 343 installation, in 2006, of 7 metallic trihedral CRs (Fig. 15) to be observed with the ENVISAT (C-band,
 344 with a 35-day revisiting period). The Vallcebre landslide movement is favorably oriented (towards
 345 the west), and with a gentle slope. Additionally, the deformation rates are moderate enough in order
 346 to prevent, the phase from “rolling over” (problem due to the ambiguous nature of the DInSAR). One
 347 corner (CR_2) was installed directly on the stable rock to be used as reference (Fig. 23). The maximum
 348 distance between the corners was 300 m to keep the atmospheric bias negligible. The installation was
 349 done with utmost care, with the CR symmetry axis oriented towards the satellite orbit [8].
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Figure 15. Corner Reflectors (CRs) used for DInSAR monitoring at the Vallcebre landslide [8].
Examples of installation on a big rock block (left) or directly over the terrain (right).

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In the Fig. 16a the CRs are clearly distinguishable in an amplitude image of the landslide. Processing interferometrically four 2007 descending ENVISAT images, the map of the rate of movements was obtained (Fig. 16b). As an example, the Fig. 17 displays the resulting displacements, which were small between the end of December 2006 and the beginning of March 2007, whereas for CR1 and CR4 there is a substantial increase in March and April associated with an abundant rainfall period.

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Figure 16. Left: the 7 Corner Reflectors appear as bright spots in a 2007 radar amplitude image. Right: the concentric circles on the map represent the rate of movement of the CRs during the first half of 2007.

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Figure 17. Evolution of the displacements (cm) of the CRs during the first half of 2007. The relative L.O.S. displacement was corrected to the direction of the maximum local slope. Precipitation (mm) is also presented as vertical bars.

377 *2.6. Non-interferometric GBSAR monitoring*

378 [23, 24] presented the application of the Ground-Based SAR (GBSAR) to landslides. In 2010-2011,
379 the lower part of the Vallcebre landslide was monitored using a GBSAR. In this case, we did not use
380 interferometry based on the phase but a new procedure to process the amplitude component of the
381 GBSAR data acquired in discontinuous mode. This methodology intends to overcome several well-
382 known drawbacks of the radar interferometry, especially in a landslide environment: loss of
383 coherence; lapse of time between acquisitions; aliasing effect; atmosphere influence, and so on. The
384 use of geometric features of the amplitude images combined with a matching technique is fully
385 described in [9].

386 Between February 2010 and September 2011, this technique was applied to the lower unit of the
387 Vallcebre landslide in order to evaluate the performance of the non-interferometric GBSAR approach.
388 In this period, eight measurement campaigns were carried out using the IBIS-L Ku-band GBSAR (IDS
389 SpA, Fig. 18). In each campaign, 15 small CRs (Fig. 19) were deployed in and around the target area
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Figure 18. Picture of the IDS GBSAR system. The synthetic aperture is obtained through the movement of the radar sensor (yellow box) along the rail.

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410 **Figure 19.** One of the small Corner Reflectors deployed over the landslide lower unit in order to fix
411 up the vegetation and snow problems. The operator is holding a surveying circular prism, which is
412 observed from a reference point with a Total Station, for validation purposes.

413 In parallel to the GBSAR measurements, five Total Station surveying campaigns were carried
414 out to validate the results obtained with the GBSAR. The analysis of the total measurements obtained
415 during the 19 months permitted the validation of the technique. Displacements up to 80 cm were
416 measured in the lower part of the lower unit (Fig. 20).

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419 **Figure 20.** L.O.S. displacements measured with non-interferometric GBSAR between February 2010
420 and September 2011 at eight small CRs. The CR14, in a stable zone, acts as reference CR.

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422 **3. Discussion**

423 As the different systems were applied to certain common points, the resulting displacements
 424 can be compared, and practical precisions, advantages and drawbacks may be derived.

425 For the superficial methods, we observed that the GPS measurements show better trends and
 426 stability than the Total Station measurements, at least with the Vallcebre conditions and equipment.
 427 An example is given in Fig. 21. Moreover, the GPS surveying is “all-weather” in practice, an
 428 additional advantage when working in mountainous areas. A theoretical composition of errors, along
 429 with independent checks of the GPS-RTK results obtained at fixed stable points, let us establish the
 430 following standard deviations [7]: 16 mm in the horizontal plane and 24 mm in elevation. The GPS
 431 network in Vallcebre is still in use.

432 The GPS measurements were also used to check inclinometer and wire extensometer
 433 displacements at several boreholes [6]. As an example, in Fig. 22 a cross-check is presented. In
 434 Vallcebre, the inclinometric readings were possible only until 200 mm of total displacement for the
 435 top of the boreholes, due to the casing deformation in the failure zone. Nevertheless, the wire
 436 extensometers and GPS measurements have been continued without trouble beyond these figures.

437 Compared with the standard GPS (campaign by campaign), the extensometric technique has the
 438 advantage of being an automatic and continuous measuring system which can be correlated with
 439 rainfall and piezometric heads. On the other hand, the GPS yields the direction of the movement and
 440 the ΔZ as well as the $\Delta Distance$. It is worth noting that the GPS can also be installed and operated in
 441 continuous ([17] for instance).

463 **Figure 21.** Apparent change in the behaviour of point G2 when monitored with classical surveying
 464 (dots 1 to 12) or with GPS (dots 12 to 18). Blue arrow points towards the Total Station.

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Figure 22. Comparison of the corrected wire extensometer displacement (D_h) against the GPS and the inclinometric measurements of the Vallcebre borehole S2.

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The cross-checking was also useful for the radar measurements, validating or improving the remote sensing techniques. Every GPS campaign included the CR and the borehole heads (Fig. 23). For instance, in Fig. 24 a phase unwrapping problem is recovered. The figure shows two displacement time series of CR_4. The continuous blue line represents one phase unwrapping solution, which has an accumulated displacement of 6.9 cm and which shows an upward displacement of 1.1 cm between April and June 2008. Considering the kinematics of the landslide, this type of movement can be considered very unlikely. For this reason, a second solution was chosen, depicted with a dashed line and which shows an accumulated displacement of 11.9 cm in 11 months. The same figure shows the displacement measured by the wire extensometer S5 (green curve), which is located relatively close to CR_4. It is interesting to compare the time series of CR_4 (dashed line) and S5. They display quite a similar temporal evolution, which includes a strong deformation gradient between June and July, followed by a stationary period until September and a second, less strong deformation gradient. This similarity confirms the one phase shift applied to the CR_4 curve. The curves do not fully overlap because one point is 84 m from the other.

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Figure 23. Cross-checking between techniques: every GPS campaign included the CRs (CR_2 in the picture) and the top of the boreholes where the wire extensometers and/or the inclinometers were installed.

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Figure 24. Displacement time series estimated with DInSAR over the CR_4 Corner Reflector, and measured by the wire-extensometer S5, located at a distance of 84m. A DInSAR ambiguity is shown in red.

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The GBSAR amplitude technique presented in #2.6 was also validated against the continuous monitoring given by the wire extensometer system. Prior to performing a proper comparison, the CR5 and CR7 Line-Of-Sight (LOS) results (Fig. 20) must be projected onto the total displacement vector (estimated from GPS measurements in the area). The method can be found in [9] and is outlined in Fig. 25.

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Figure 25. The GBSAR total displacement, D_T , is computed from D_{LOS} using the 3D average direction derived from GPS (unit vector U_T) [9].

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After the projection, the CR5 and CR7 GBSAR displacements can be compared with the closer wire extensometer (S11 and S2 respectively, Fig. 26). Dashed straight lines have a 1:1 slope, i.e., the perfect fit, which is almost reached.

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Figure 26. Charts showing GBSAR total displacement, D_T , against wire extensometer displacement, D_W : (a) for CR5 and S11, and (b) for CR7 and S2.

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Finally, after all this precision considerations and system crosschecks, the SAR and/or cable displacements can be visualized as 3D vectors, the 3D direction is given by the GPS data (Fig. 27).

549 4. Summary and conclusions

550 A general overview of the methods used in Vallcebre for measuring the displacements of the
551 landslide has been given. More details of the systems presented here in abstract, along with the full
552 formulation, validation and conclusions can be found in [1, 8, 9]. To conclude, we present here some
553 lessons learned during the progressive monitoring of the Vallcebre landslide since 1987.

554 A summary of the main characteristics of the methods is given in Table 1. This table is in
555 accordance with [4, 7], but the values are valid only for the specific constraints and equipment in
556 Vallcebre. The characteristics of the methods are summarized along with the precision and main
557 results achieved. The 'Precision' figures try to characterize the 'real' or field performance of the
558 systems in our landslide instead of the theoretical values that can be found in the instrument's
559 technical specifications. The later are determined in lab conditions and are too optimistic, in general.
560 The 'Complexity' column aims to quantify the refinement of the equipment and personnel involved,
561 and the 'Cost' column includes the amount of instrumentation, installation and work needed to
562 obtain the data.

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Figure 27. Displacement field of the lower unit of the Vallcebre landslide reconstructed using GBSAR CRs and borehole wire extensometers (S). The yellow figures, in cm, are the total displacements observed from February to November 2010 [9].

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Table 1. Overview of the methods used in Vallcebre landslide monitoring

	Method	Results	Typical range in Vallcebre	Typical precision in Vallcebre	Comple-xity	Cost	Comments
Surface	Terrestrial Photogrammetry	Maps (points with $\Delta X, \Delta Y, \Delta Z$, contour lines)	30 to 45 m	10 mm for well-defined points	Medium	High	High precision equipment and skill is needed ^b
	EDM& Theodolite	$\Delta dist.$ or $\Delta X, \Delta Y, \Delta Z$	15 to 1500 m	7 mm for $\Delta dist.$, >25 mm for the rest	Medium	Low	Practical experience in surveying is needed ^c

	GPS ^d	$\Delta X, \Delta Y, \Delta Z$	800 to 2300 m	12-16 mm (horiz.) 18-24 mm (elev.)	Low	Low	Discontinuous over time ^c
	CR based DInSAR	Displacement L.O.S.	Non applicable	a few mm	High	High	Each 35 days with Envisat
	Non-interferometric GBSAR	Displacement L.O.S.	500-800m	below 1 cm	High	High	Continuous. CRs must be installed each campaign
	Distributed Fiber Optics (in trench) ^e	Zones with strain changes	Non available	Non available	High	High	Not installed yet
In-hole	Inclinometer	$\Delta X, \Delta Y$	15 to 45 m depth	1 to 2 mm	Low	Medium	Discontinuous over time ^c
	Wire extensometer ^d	$\Delta D_{wire} \rightarrow \Delta D_{horiz}, \Delta D_{vert}$	15 to 45 m depth	0.5 mm in the wire length ^a	Low	Medium	Continuous log, discontinuous/continuous download
	Piezometer ^d	$\Delta P_w \sim \Delta H_w$	15 to 45 m depth	30mm water head	Low	Low-Medium	Continuous log, discontinuous/continuous download

a: Wire extensometer. After calibration of the wire equation, 2 mm in the surface displacement can be achieved.

b: The application of Terrestrial or Low-aerial photogram. is becoming easier because improvements like drones and VSfM based SW..

c: The technique, with a slightly different setup, may become continuous (continuous GPS, Robotic Total Station, In-Place-Inclinometer.

d: GPS, Wire extensometer and Piezometer are green because they are still operational

e: Distributed Fiber Optics is red because it has not yet been applied.

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The methods in the table should not be considered as excluding alternatives but as complementary systems to be applied progressively or in different areas, as has been explained in section 2. For instance, the photogrammetry was used in the toe of the slide to monitor a fairly small but very active area. The EDM & triangulation (and later the GPS) were implemented to cover the whole hillside and capture mean movements as big as 1 meter per year with minimum investment.

The surveying with EDM and GPS were carried out with a given frequency (i.e. campaigns each two months or each year), so the results are discontinuous over time. As stated in the note 'c' in Table 1, although not implemented in Vallcebre, it is technically possible to automate the procedure for the continuous monitoring of the displacements.

On the other hand, the GPS results helped to calibrate the parameters of the wire extensometer equation [6]. The installation of these in-hole devices was possible only when additional funding was obtained in order to drill the boreholes and instrument them. The inclinometers and the in-hole wire extensometers complement each other very well. As the landslide was fairly active, the inclinometers had a short 'life', but produced high-quality information on landslide displacement profiles, velocities and the position of the shear surface quite immediately after their installation. In contrast, at the early stages of deformation, the wire extensometers may only record negative displacements, which are not easily related to the superficial ones. However, once the inclinometers were lost, the wire extensometers have allowed continuous recording, even for very large displacements. Since 1996, when they were first installed, the wire extensometers have provided a measurement readout each 20 minutes and, at some points, the cumulative displacement has been as high as 6 m. The accelerations in the rate of displacement can be easily related to rainfall and groundwater rises (Fig. 14), especially during critical rainy events, when other systems are not in operation. Most of the piezometers and 3 wire extensometers installed in Vallcebre were still operational in 2012. Around 2010 an automatic meteorological station was installed in the centre of the landslide in order to get the significant precipitation, because the rainfall may vary sharply from one point to another.

The redundancy between methods is very advisable so as to detect malfunctions of the devices, or cover gaps in data. As shown in the previous sections, all the results are in fairly good accordance when adequate corrections are done (Fig. 22 and 23). Prior to the comparison of the different techniques, some error considerations must be done, in particular the filtering of any systematic

607 errors (Fig. 24 and 25, for instance). In order to filter ‘automatically’ some systematic errors, during
 608 the monitoring operation (acquisition and data handling) it is convenient to be very ‘systematic’ (to
 609 follow exactly the same field and processing procedures).

610 Contrary to structural monitoring, when working with natural materials like soils and rock, we
 611 do have to accept their natural variability. To cover this variability, it is better tending to continuous
 612 techniques, both in the Time domain and in the Spatial domain (Fig. 28).

623 **Figure 28.** Tentative disposition of the different techniques used in Vallcebre according their
 624 continuity in the Spatial and temporal domain. Distributed Fiber Optics is in red because it has not
 625 yet been applied. The asterisks indicate that the technique, with a slightly different setup, may become
 626 continuous over space or time.

627 The systems that were operated continuously along the time rely on automatic acquisition. We
 628 have learned that ‘automatic’ does not means ‘free of maintenance’. On the contrary, the continuous
 629 systems need a continuous surveillance and maintenance [2]. Another recommendation for long-term
 630 monitoring networks: when feasible, it is better to avoid points or benchmarks that may exhibit own
 631 movements (large boulders, light poles, trees, concrete pillars, old stone walls and so on). The discreet
 632 and sturdy marking of points diminish natural disturbance and vandalism. Finally yet importantly,
 633 it is mandatory to include within the network several fixed points in stable areas around the landslide
 634 for checking purposes.

635 With the years, some improvements in the electrical supply (solar panels) and in the data
 636 transmission (remote download) have been introduced in the Vallcebre set-up. Currently, the wire
 637 extensometer and the piezometer readings can be downloaded from a remote location by means of
 638 the mobile phone network in order to get the monitoring of the landslide in real time in the command
 639 headquarters.

640 All the works described so far allow qualifying the Vallcebre landslide as a real-scale “in situ”
 641 lab or observatory. The relatively slow rate of motion and the sustained long-term mobility made it
 642 suitable for the testing and validation of several new systems within European and National Projects.
 643 In the next future, we plan to install an experimental array of Distributed Fiber Optics (25) in order
 644 to assess its field performance. The projected array includes around 600 meters of FO buried in a
 645 trench following a country road, roughly along the 1000m contour line in Fig. 27. This area is
 646 subjected to shear displacements produced by the landslide lateral limits and the transition from the
 647 middle to the lower unit. The wire extensometer and the GPS control points present in the zone will
 648 permit the cross-calibration of the FO array results and performance.

649 The basic research on the performance of the different instruments and methods that are carried
 650 out in the Vallcebre landslide should help to choose the monitoring strategy in new real sites. In doing
 651 this, we must bear in mind that the monitoring must address some fundamental geotechnical
 652 questions [26, 27]. Instruments and methods that help to answer these questions should be selected.
 653 As John Dunniciiff stated, *"If there is no question, there should be no instrumentation"*.
 654

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 656 and processing, MC and OM; data analysis and validation, JAG and JM; supervision and search for funding, JC
 657 and JM; writing, JAG. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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